

SOSCHI

Standards for Official Statistics on
Climate-Health Interactions

Metadata Sheet: Malaria incidence attributable to extreme rainfall

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The methods for measuring this indicator were endorsed by the 57th United Nations Statistical Commission to include in the Global Set of Climate Change Statistics and Indicators (see decision 57/109 (b) in the [Final Report](#)).

This will be included in the [Global Set](#) and metadata as:

Indicator 44: Incidence of cases of climate-related disease:

Incidence of malaria cases attributable to (a) heat and (b) rainfall

1. Indicator key information

Current publication date 7 May 2026		Previous publication date 28 February 2025
Topic area Vector-borne diseases	Indicator name Malaria incidence attributable to extreme rainfall	Tier 2 (provisional)
Unit of measure		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relative risk (RR): Relative risk of malaria cases attributable to extreme rainfall • Attributable number (AN): Number of malaria cases attributable to extreme rainfall • Attributable fraction (AF): Fraction of malaria cases attributable to extreme rainfall • Attributable rate (AR): Malaria cases per 100,000 population attributable to extreme rainfall 		
Sub-indicators Not applicable to this indicator		
Disaggregation By sex, age group, socio-economic group, ethnic group, occupation		
Temporal breakdown Monthly data for a yearly statistic		Geographical coverage National, Regional, Subregional, Local
Purpose This indicator measures the excess risk of confirmed malaria cases attributable to extreme rainfall, defined as unusually dry or unusually wet conditions within a specified period. It captures the contribution of rainfall extremes to fluctuations in malaria incidence and, when disaggregated by region, sex, and age, provides insights into population-level differences in vulnerability. Estimates are generally produced at the monthly scale due to current data constraints, though finer temporal resolutions (weekly or daily) may be applied where feasible. The indicator provides robust evidence on the health impacts of rainfall extremes on malaria, supports the monitoring of spatial and temporal trends, and informs the design of climate-resilient public health and adaptation strategies.		
Relevance & rationale Malaria incidence is highly sensitive to extreme rainfall, as unusually heavy rainfall and prolonged dry periods alter mosquito breeding habitats, transmission cycles, and human exposure to the disease. ^{1,2} This indicator quantifies the excess burden of malaria linked to rainfall extremes, complementing SDG 3.3.3 (malaria incidence per 1,000 at risk) and enabling disaggregation by age, sex, and region. ^{3,4} It supports assessment of health system vulnerability, guides adaptation and control strategies, and aligns with international commitments under the SDGs, the Sendai Framework (targets A and B), and the Paris Agreement (Article 7). ⁵		

See section 1.1 of the [Vector-borne diseases \(malaria\) and climate: Topic Introduction](#) for more details.

Confounders and modifiers

Multiple environmental, social, and health system factors influence the association between extreme rainfall and malaria incidence. Important effect modifiers include antecedent rainfall conditions, temperature, relative humidity, ecological setting, vector control coverage, and population vulnerability (e.g., children under five, pregnant women).^{3,6} Key confounders are socioeconomic status, access to healthcare and surveillance systems, baseline transmission intensity, migration and mobility patterns, agricultural and labour practices, and broader climate variability (e.g., El Niño/La Niña).⁷ Adjusting for these factors in statistical models is essential to ensure accurate attribution of malaria cases to rainfall extremes and to generate robust, comparable estimates across countries and regions.⁸

See section 3.5 of the [Malaria incidence attributable to extreme temperature and extreme rainfall: methodology](#) for more detail.

Data Sources

It is advisable to use official data sources are used where possible:

- Monthly malaria cases and demographic data: from national administrative records
- Monthly rainfall and other climate data: from governmental meteorological offices

If these official data sources are not available there are suggestions of alternative global datasets as proxy sources outlined in section 2.2 of the [Malaria incidence attributable to extreme temperature and extreme rainfall: methodology](#).

Data limitations

In some settings, malaria cases may not be entered into reporting systems immediately, creating a lag between the time of illness and official registration. Producing very up-to-date statistics can therefore reduce the dataset's completeness. It is important to strike a balance between timeliness and coverage. Moreover, malaria episodes treated outside formal health facilities may not be captured in hospital records, a point to consider when interpreting the indicator.

Methodology

The statistical method for this indicator uses a spatiotemporal Bayesian hierarchical model linked with a distributed lag nonlinear model (DLNM). Estimation is performed with the Integrated Nested Laplace Approximation (INLA) via the R-INLA package, adapting approaches described by Blangiardo et al.,⁹ Lowe et al.,¹⁰ and Rachmawati et al.¹¹ The framework developed by Lowe et al.¹⁰ has been tailored here to examine how extreme rainfall influences malaria incidence over time, while also adjusting for temperature, humidity, and drought conditions as potential confounders. The outcome variable is the monthly count of reported malaria cases at the subnational level, ideally spanning at least 3 years. A Poisson specification is applied to model case counts, complemented by spatiotemporal random effects to capture unmeasured variation, seasonal cycles, and spatial correlation across regions.

Within this structure, the DLNM component applies cross-basis functions to estimate both the nonlinear rainfall-response curve and delayed effects across several months.¹²

Relative risks (RR) for malaria are then derived across rainfall ranges and lags. Using the posterior estimates and their uncertainty distributions, the model produces RR curves that are subsequently used to calculate the attributable number (AN), attributable fraction (AF), and attributable rate (AR) of malaria cases linked to extreme rainfall exposure, following the approach of Gasparrini and Leone.¹²

The workflow proceeds in three stages:

- Estimate a spatiotemporal Bayesian hierarchical model with DLNM using monthly malaria and climate data.
- Use posterior model outputs to generate rainfall-specific relative risks.
- Calculate ANs, AFs, and ARs of malaria cases attributable to extreme rainfall, with uncertainty intervals, for each geographic unit and year.

Further details on parameter settings, model diagnostics, and sensitivity tests are available in sections 3.4 to 3.7 of the [Malaria incidence attributable to extreme temperature and extreme rainfall: methodology](#).

Methodology limitations

Some limitations should be considered when interpreting results from this indicator.

- The population offset in the R-INLA model is not disaggregated by age group, potentially masking differences in susceptibility across demographic groups and regions with varying population growth rates.
- The spatial structure assumes connectivity only within national boundaries, so border areas may be influenced by neighbouring regions in other countries that are not captured in the model.¹⁰
- The Distributed Lag Non-Linear Model (DLNM) component is sensitive to how the exposure-response and lag-response relationships are defined; inappropriate parameter choices can lead to overfitting or over-smoothing.^{13,14}
- The model assumes a uniform lag structure across space and time, which may not reflect local or seasonal differences.¹²
- Stable estimation of exposure-lag-response relationships requires at least 3 years of continuous data, ideally 5 or more, to capture long-term variability and extreme events.

For more information on the methodology limitations see section 5 of the [Malaria incidence attributable to extreme temperature and extreme rainfall: methodology](#).

Interpretation & communication

The components of this indicator are best presented by a combination of statistical tables and graphs. Examples of outputs produced and further guidance are specified in Table 5 of the [Malaria incidence attributable to extreme temperature and extreme rainfall: methodology](#).

Recommendations for future developments

For future development, priority will be given to:

- Economic burden of malaria cases attributable to extreme rainfall

The following indicators proposed in the topic introduction documentation will also be considered:

- Dengue cases attributable to extreme temperature

<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Dengue cases attributable to extreme rainfall• Malaria hospital admission cases attributable to flood severity.• Malaria deaths attributable to flood severity	
Link to R package The climatehealth R package is available via the SOSCHI GitHub repository or CRAN	Link to the indicator tool on the platform Climate-Health Platform (in development)
Links to relevant indicators within the SOSCHI framework <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Topic Introduction: Temperature-related health effects• Topic Introduction: Health effects of flooding	
Links to existing indicators and statistics: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• SDGs: Target 3.3• Paris Agreement: Article 7; 13.8• Sendai Framework: Target A and B• UN Global Set: 44. Incidence of cases of climate-related diseases• Lancet Countdown: Similar indicator – 1.3.2 Malaria, 2.3.1 Vulnerability to Mosquito-borne Disease• FDES: 5.2.3. Targets vector-borne diseases, including the spread of diseases like malaria through vectors.	
Additional notes and comments	

2. References

1. Liu Q, Wang Y, Deng J, Yan W, Qin C, Du M, et al. Association of temperature and precipitation with malaria incidence in 57 countries and territories from 2000 to 2019: A worldwide observational study. *J Glob Health*. 2024;14:04021. doi:10.7189/jogh.14.04021 PubMed PMID: 38385445; PubMed Central PMCID: PMC10882640.
2. Mafwele BJ, Lee JW. Relationships between transmission of malaria in Africa and climate factors. *Sci Rep*. 2022 Aug 23;12(1):14392. doi:10.1038/s41598-022-18782-9
3. Mangusho C, Mwebesa E, Izudi J, Aleni M, Dricile R, Ayiasi RM, et al. High prevalence of malaria in pregnancy among women attending antenatal care at a large referral hospital in northwestern Uganda: A cross-sectional study. *PLOS ONE*. 2023 Apr 5;18(4):e0283755. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0283755 PubMed PMID: 37018283; PubMed Central PMCID: PMC10075480.
4. World Health Organization (WHO). SDG Indicator metadata [Internet]. 2025 [cited 2025 Sep 3]. Available from: <https://unstats.un.org/sdgs/metadata/files/Metadata-03-03-03.docx>
5. United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction (UNISDR). Indicators to Monitor Global Targets of the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015-2030: A Technical Review [Internet]. 2015. Report No. Available from: https://www.preventionweb.net/files/45466_indicatorspaperaugust2015final.pdf?startDownload=true
6. Chapoterera B, Naidoo K, Marume A. Impact of climate change on malaria transmission in Africa: A scoping review of literature. *J Public Health Afr*. 2025 Aug 28;16(1):13. Located at: Age; Gender. doi:10.4102/jphia.v16i1.1346
7. IPCC. Climate Change 2022 – Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability: Working Group II Contribution to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change [Internet]. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press; 2023 [cited 2023 Sep 5]. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781009325844> doi:10.1017/9781009325844
8. World Health Organization (WHO). World health statistics 2025: monitoring health for the SDGs, Sustainable Development Goals [Internet]. Geneva; 2025 [cited 2025 Jul 16]. Report No. Available from: <https://iris.who.int/bitstream/handle/10665/381418/9789240110496-eng.pdf?sequence=1>
9. Blangiardo M, Cameletti M, Baio G, Rue H. Spatial and spatio-temporal models with R-INLA. *Spat Spatio-Temporal Epidemiol*. 2013 Dec 1;7:39–55. doi:10.1016/j.sste.2013.07.003

10. Lowe R, Lee SA, O'Reilly KM, Brady OJ, Bastos L, Carrasco-Escobar G, et al. Combined effects of hydrometeorological hazards and urbanisation on dengue risk in Brazil: a spatiotemporal modelling study. *Lancet Planet Health*. 2021 Apr 1;5(4):e209–19. doi:10.1016/S2542-5196(20)30292-8
11. Rachmawati RN, Djuraidah A, Fitrianto A, Sumertajaya IM. Spatio-temporal Models Using R-INLA with Generalized Extreme Value Distribution in Hierarchical Bayes Regression. *Int J Sci Res Sci Eng Technol [Internet]*. 2018 Apr [cited 2025 Jan 16];4(4):pp.1129-1143. Available from: https://www.academia.edu/37077680/Spatio_temporal_Models_Using_R_INLA_with_Generalized_Extreme_Value_Distribution_in_Hierarchical_Bayes_Regression
12. Gasparrini A, Leone M. Attributable risk from distributed lag models. *BMC Med Res Methodol*. 2014 Apr 23;14(1):55. doi:10.1186/1471-2288-14-55
13. Armstrong BG, Gasparrini A, Tobias A. Conditional Poisson models: a flexible alternative to conditional logistic case cross-over analysis. *BMC Med Res Methodol*. 2014 Nov 24;14(1):122. doi:10.1186/1471-2288-14-122
14. Guo Y, Gasparrini A, Armstrong BG, Tawatsupa B, Tobias A, Lavigne E, et al. Heat Wave and Mortality: A Multicountry, Multicommunity Study. *Environ Health Perspect*. 2017 Aug 10;125(8):087006. doi:10.1289/EHP1026 PubMed PMID: 28886602; PubMed Central PMCID: PMC5783630.
15. Aarup T, Abdallah C, Abela-Ridder B, Abrahams J, Adamczyk S, Ahmed K, et al. Hazard Information Profiles: Supplement to UNDRR-ISC Hazard Definition & Classification Review – Technical Report [Internet]. International Science Council; 2021 Oct [cited 2025 Sep 2]. Report No. Available from: <https://council.science/publications/hazard-information-profiles/> doi:10.24948/2021.05
16. Wan K, Feng Z, Hajat S, Doherty RM. Temperature-related mortality and associated vulnerabilities: evidence from Scotland using extended time-series datasets. *Environ Health*. 2022 Oct 25;21(1):99. doi:10.1186/s12940-022-00912-5
17. WHO. World malaria report 2023 [Internet]. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2023 [cited 2024 Jul 5]. Report No. Available from: <https://www.who.int/teams/global-malaria-programme/reports/world-malaria-report-2023>

3. Abbreviations

A	AF	Attributable Fraction
	AIMSRIC	African Institute for Mathematical Sciences Research and Innovation Centre
	AN	Attributable Number
	AR	Attributable Rate
C	CRAN	Comprehensive R Archive Network
D	DLNM	Distributed Lag Non-linear Model
F	FDES	Framework for the Development of Environment Statistics
I	INLA	Integrated Nested Laplace Approximation
	IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
O	ONS	Office for National Statistics (UK)
R	RIPS	Regional Institute for Population Studies, University of Ghana, Legon
	RR	Relative Risk
S	SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
	SOSCHI	Standards for Official Statistics on Climate-Health Interactions
	SPI	Standardized Rainfall Index
U	UK	United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland
	UKHSA	United Kingdom Health Security Agency
	UN	United Nation
	UNDP	United Nations Development Programme
W	WHO	World Health Organization

4. Glossary

A	Attributable number	The estimated number of malaria cases attributable to extreme temperatures, that is, those that would not have occurred if there had been no exposure to extreme temperatures.
	Attributable rate	The estimated number of malaria cases per 100,000 population that are attributable to extreme temperatures, that is, that would not have occurred if there had been no exposure to extreme temperatures.
C	Climate hazard	A process, phenomenon, or human activity that may cause loss of life, injury, or other health impacts, property damage, social and economic disruption, or environmental degradation. ¹⁵
D	Disaggregations	These show different results for the same indicator across population subgroups or geographical divisions.
	Distributed lag non-linear model	A model often used to describe an exposure-time-response relationship in which the exposure effect is non-linear and can be delayed.
E	Extreme temperature	Extreme temperature is defined based on the estimated exposure-response relationship between temperature and malaria risk, rather than using fixed percentile thresholds. This risk-based approach allows the identification of temperature ranges where malaria risk increases significantly. ¹⁶

	Extreme rainfall	Extreme rainfall is defined based on the estimated exposure–response relationship between rainfall and malaria risk, rather than using fixed percentile thresholds. This risk-based approach allows the identification of rainfall ranges where malaria risk increases significantly ¹⁶
G	Geographic coverage	This describes the locations or areas of interest covered by the data source. This is a generic term that can be applied at the national (country-level) or sub-national level, defined using specific boundaries relevant to user needs and data availability.
M	Malaria cases	Malaria cases are the number of confirmed malaria infections within a given population and time period, identified through parasite-based diagnostic testing (microscopy or rapid diagnostic tests) or, where testing is not available, through clinical diagnosis consistent with WHO case definitions. ¹⁷
R	Relative risk	The relative risk (RR) for malaria cases attributable to extreme temperatures refers to the probability of an individual being reported with malaria during, or shortly after, exposure to extreme temperatures. An RR value of 1 indicates no difference in risk-meaning exposure to the specified extreme temperature does not increase or decrease the likelihood of being reported with malaria cases compared to the reference temperature.

S	Sub-indicator(s)	These are a subset of the headline outcome indicator and provide additional diagnostic criteria or other definitions.
	Sub-national	Any level of geographical disaggregation below the national level. This can be defined using geographic boundaries that are relevant to the user's needs and data availability.
T	Tier score	This is an indicator maturity score, based on 3 tiers. The approach to tier classification is explained in section 5.3 of the SOSCHI framework report. This is a provisional approach; given that the classification requires information on data availability globally, the definitive classification of a tier needed for the UN Global Set requires a global consultation.

5. Important notes

5.1 Reproducible code library

An open-source climatehealth R package, developed for the calculation of this indicator, can be found on the SOSCHI GitHub. This code can be adapted to users' own needs and data requirements. To use this code, see the following sections of the [methodology document](#):

- section 2.3 data template: information to set up your dataset
- section 3.1 for an overview of what is included in the scope of this code
- section 6.2 for further guidance on running analysis using the climatehealth R package

You will need a GitHub account and R version 4.4.1 or later. Access the GitHub repository for this indicator at <https://github.com/onssoschi/climatehealth>.

5.1 Statistics in development

This document has been published as part of the final version of the SOSCHI statistical framework. However, given that these are new methods with limited global implementation, future modifications may be required based on user feedback and advancements in the scientific literature.

Statistics within this document are therefore considered statistics in development. See our [Guide to official statistics in development](#) for more information about what this means.

5.2 Licensing and reproduction

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Statistical data used in the preparation of this document may be confidential under UK or other national laws. Enquiries regarding data availability can be made to the project team at climate.health@ons.gov.uk.

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Overview of the SOSCHI project

The impacts on health of rising temperatures, wildfires, extreme weather events and other direct and indirect effects of climate change are a major global concern. The most significant hazards and their impacts differ between countries and regions, as do the possibilities and priorities for climate change adaptation. National and local governments and other stakeholders need to have regular, reliable and comparable data to monitor climate impacts and inform adaptation strategies, based on a transparent and globally generalisable statistical framework. The SOSCHI project, led by the UK Office for National Statistics and funded by Wellcome, is developing a framework of indicators based on state-of-the-art statistical methods to measure climate-related health risks. To support global reporting and monitoring, we are also developing a knowledge-sharing platform, open-source tools, and R code. Our findings will also help highlight data gaps and help set the agenda for future improvement of data sources and methods.

Project partners

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